

Simulation Data for Few-Shot, Robust Calibration of Single Qubit Gates Using Bayesian Robust Phase Estimation

Travis Hurant*

*Duke Quantum Center, Duke University, Durham, NC 27701, USA and
Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Duke University, Durham, NC 27708 USA*

Ke Sun

*Duke Quantum Center, Duke University, Durham, NC 27701, USA and
Department of Physics, Duke University, Durham, NC 27708 USA*

Zhubing Jia

*Duke Quantum Center, Duke University, Durham, NC 27701, USA
Department of Physics, Duke University, Durham, NC 27708 USA and
Present address: Department of Physics, The University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, Urbana, IL, USA*

Jungsang Kim

*Duke Quantum Center, Duke University, Durham, NC 27701, USA
Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Duke University, Durham, NC 27708 USA and
Department of Physics, Duke University, Durham, NC 27708 USA*

Kenneth R. Brown

*Duke Quantum Center, Duke University, Durham, NC 27701, USA
Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Duke University, Durham, NC 27708 USA
Department of Physics, Duke University, Durham, NC 27708 USA and
Department of Chemistry, Duke University, Durham, NC 27708 USA*

* travis.hurant@duke.edu

I. OVERVIEW

Bayesian Robust Phase Estimation (BRPE) enhances the traditional Robust Phase Estimation (RPE) [1] by incorporating Bayesian parameter estimation techniques to minimize sampling overhead. We simulated both BRPE and RPE in error-free environments and in settings affected by measurement errors, depolarizing errors, and state preparation and measurement (SPAM) errors. This document presents statistical outcomes from these simulations.

II. ERROR-FREE SIMULATIONS

TABLE I: Performance Metrics in an Error Free Environment

M_k	RPE		BRPE		% Decrease in $\bar{\epsilon}$
	$\bar{\epsilon}$	$\bar{\epsilon} < \bar{\epsilon}_{th}$	$\bar{\epsilon}$	$\bar{\epsilon} < \bar{\epsilon}_{th}$	
4	$3.5 \times 10^{-2} \pm 2.5 \times 10^{-2}$	Yes	$1.4 \times 10^{-3} \pm 1.2 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$96.08\% \pm 4.34\%$
8	$1.2 \times 10^{-3} \pm 1.4 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$1.83 \times 10^{-4} \pm 2.4 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$85.08\% \pm 17.48\%$
16	$1.68 \times 10^{-4} \pm 1.7 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$1.26 \times 10^{-4} \pm 1.7 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$24.97\% \pm 12.51\%$
32	$1.2 \times 10^{-4} \pm 1.4 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$8.7 \times 10^{-5} \pm 1.2 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$27.13\% \pm 12.99\%$
64	$8.41 \times 10^{-5} \pm 9.7 \times 10^{-6}$	Yes	$6.05 \times 10^{-5} \pm 8.3 \times 10^{-6}$	Yes	$28.02\% \pm 12.92\%$
128	$5.93 \times 10^{-5} \pm 7.1 \times 10^{-6}$	Yes	$4.23 \times 10^{-5} \pm 5.8 \times 10^{-6}$	Yes	$28.62\% \pm 12.98\%$

III. SIMULATIONS WITH MEASUREMENT ERROR

TABLE II: BRPE and RPE Performance Metrics with Measurement Error

p	M_k	RPE		BRPE		% Decrease in $\bar{\epsilon}$
		$\bar{\epsilon}$	$\bar{\epsilon} < \bar{\epsilon}_{th}$	$\bar{\epsilon}$	$\bar{\epsilon} < \bar{\epsilon}_{th}$	
0.005	8	$1.4 \times 10^{-3} \pm 1.8 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$1.95 \times 10^{-4} \pm 1.4 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$86.40\% \pm 16.75\%$
	16	$1.69 \times 10^{-4} \pm 1.6 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$1.37 \times 10^{-4} \pm 1.5 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$18.68\% \pm 11.86\%$
	32	$1.2 \times 10^{-4} \pm 1.3 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$9.8 \times 10^{-5} \pm 2.2 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$18.20\% \pm 20.32\%$
	64	$8.5 \times 10^{-5} \pm 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$7.2 \times 10^{-5} \pm 2.6 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$15.81\% \pm 32.72\%$
	128	$6.05 \times 10^{-5} \pm 6.9 \times 10^{-6}$	Yes	$5.4 \times 10^{-5} \pm 3.0 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$10.05\% \pm 50.40\%$
0.01	8	$2.5 \times 10^{-3} \pm 3.7 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$2.14 \times 10^{-4} \pm 6.2 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$91.49\% \pm 12.69\%$
	16	$1.72 \times 10^{-4} \pm 1.6 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$1.47 \times 10^{-4} \pm 3.1 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$14.54\% \pm 19.84\%$
	32	$1.22 \times 10^{-4} \pm 1.3 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$1.08 \times 10^{-4} \pm 3.9 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$11.70\% \pm 33.27\%$
	64	$8.58 \times 10^{-5} \pm 9.6 \times 10^{-6}$	Yes	$8.2 \times 10^{-5} \pm 4.4 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$4.91\% \pm 51.95\%$
	128	$6.1 \times 10^{-5} \pm 6.9 \times 10^{-6}$	Yes	$6.5 \times 10^{-5} \pm 4.7 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$-6.69\% \pm 77.52\%$
0.015	8	$2.1 \times 10^{-3} \pm 1.8 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$2.6 \times 10^{-4} \pm 2.5 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$87.57\% \pm 15.92\%$
	16	$1.76 \times 10^{-4} \pm 1.6 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$1.56 \times 10^{-4} \pm 4.5 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$11.33\% \pm 27.12\%$
	32	$1.25 \times 10^{-4} \pm 1.2 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$1.17 \times 10^{-4} \pm 5.1 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$6.17\% \pm 41.95\%$
	64	$8.7 \times 10^{-5} \pm 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$9.1 \times 10^{-5} \pm 5.7 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$-3.92\% \pm 66.43\%$
	128	$6.18 \times 10^{-5} \pm 6.6 \times 10^{-6}$	Yes	$7.6 \times 10^{-5} \pm 6.0 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$-22.44\% \pm 97.71\%$
0.02	8	$3.3 \times 10^{-3} \pm 2.7 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$2.21 \times 10^{-4} \pm 4.0 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$93.24\% \pm 5.70\%$
	16	$2.6 \times 10^{-4} \pm 4.9 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$1.64 \times 10^{-4} \pm 5.6 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$36.39\% \pm 124.09\%$
	32	$1.25 \times 10^{-4} \pm 1.2 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$1.25 \times 10^{-4} \pm 6.3 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$-0.04\% \pm 50.97\%$
	64	$8.86 \times 10^{-5} \pm 9.3 \times 10^{-6}$	Yes	$1.0 \times 10^{-4} \pm 6.8 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$-13.51\% \pm 77.24\%$
	128	$6.29 \times 10^{-5} \pm 6.7 \times 10^{-6}$	Yes	$8.6 \times 10^{-5} \pm 7.1 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$-37.28\% \pm 113.97\%$
0.025	8	$3.1 \times 10^{-3} \pm 3.3 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$2.8 \times 10^{-4} \pm 2.5 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$90.83\% \pm 12.81\%$
	16	$1.89 \times 10^{-4} \pm 6.4 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$1.71 \times 10^{-4} \pm 6.5 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$9.42\% \pm 45.90\%$
	32	$1.26 \times 10^{-4} \pm 1.2 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$1.34 \times 10^{-4} \pm 7.3 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$-6.12\% \pm 58.60\%$
	64	$9.06 \times 10^{-5} \pm 9.0 \times 10^{-6}$	Yes	$1.1 \times 10^{-4} \pm 7.7 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$-21.69\% \pm 85.58\%$
	128	$6.35 \times 10^{-5} \pm 6.7 \times 10^{-6}$	Yes	$9.6 \times 10^{-5} \pm 8.1 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$-51.86\% \pm 128.25\%$
0.03	8	$3.7 \times 10^{-3} \pm 3.3 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$2.51 \times 10^{-4} \pm 8.2 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$93.27\% \pm 6.30\%$
	16	$2.6 \times 10^{-4} \pm 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$1.8 \times 10^{-4} \pm 7.4 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$31.81\% \pm 130.80\%$
	32	$1.29 \times 10^{-4} \pm 1.3 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$1.43 \times 10^{-4} \pm 8.2 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$-11.28\% \pm 64.39\%$
	64	$9.08 \times 10^{-5} \pm 8.9 \times 10^{-6}$	Yes	$1.19 \times 10^{-4} \pm 8.6 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$-31.11\% \pm 95.58\%$
	128	$6.44 \times 10^{-5} \pm 6.6 \times 10^{-6}$	Yes	$1.06 \times 10^{-4} \pm 8.9 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$-64.75\% \pm 139.77\%$

IV. SIMULATIONS WITH DEPOLARIZING ERROR

TABLE III: BRPE and RPE Performance Metrics with Depolarizing Error

p	M_k	RPE		BRPE		% Decrease in $\bar{\epsilon}$
		$\bar{\epsilon}$	$\bar{\epsilon} < \bar{\epsilon}_{th}$	$\bar{\epsilon}$	$\bar{\epsilon} < \bar{\epsilon}_{th}$	
0.005	8	$8.6 \times 10^{-3} \pm 2.1 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$3.98 \times 10^{-3} \pm 6.6 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$53.64\% \pm 13.71\%$
	16	$4.68 \times 10^{-3} \pm 2.0 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$2.82 \times 10^{-3} \pm 6.8 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$39.78\% \pm 14.74\%$
	32	$3.55 \times 10^{-3} \pm 1.2 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$2.24 \times 10^{-3} \pm 7.4 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$37.00\% \pm 20.92\%$
	64	$2.846 \times 10^{-3} \pm 9.0 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$1.89 \times 10^{-3} \pm 8.1 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$33.67\% \pm 28.37\%$
	128	$2.367 \times 10^{-3} \pm 4.3 \times 10^{-5}$	Yes	$1.67 \times 10^{-3} \pm 8.7 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$29.37\% \pm 36.68\%$
0.01	8	$1.56 \times 10^{-2} \pm 1.7 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$8.1 \times 10^{-3} \pm 1.4 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$47.78\% \pm 10.73\%$
	16	$9.5 \times 10^{-3} \pm 4.0 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$5.7 \times 10^{-3} \pm 1.4 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$39.91\% \pm 14.97\%$
	32	$7.28 \times 10^{-3} \pm 2.2 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$4.6 \times 10^{-3} \pm 1.5 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$37.18\% \pm 20.34\%$
	64	$5.9 \times 10^{-3} \pm 1.7 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$3.9 \times 10^{-3} \pm 1.6 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$34.57\% \pm 26.38\%$
	128	$4.95 \times 10^{-3} \pm 1.5 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$3.5 \times 10^{-3} \pm 1.6 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$29.93\% \pm 33.21\%$
0.015	8	$2.33 \times 10^{-2} \pm 2.3 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$1.22 \times 10^{-2} \pm 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$47.77\% \pm 9.88\%$
	16	$1.437 \times 10^{-2} \pm 6.4 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$8.7 \times 10^{-3} \pm 2.1 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$39.54\% \pm 14.63\%$
	32	$1.087 \times 10^{-2} \pm 3.4 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$6.8 \times 10^{-3} \pm 2.2 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$37.27\% \pm 19.98\%$
	64	$8.92 \times 10^{-3} \pm 2.1 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$5.8 \times 10^{-3} \pm 2.3 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$34.88\% \pm 26.12\%$
	128	$7.55 \times 10^{-3} \pm 1.9 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$5.2 \times 10^{-3} \pm 2.4 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$30.77\% \pm 32.20\%$
0.02	8	$3.1 \times 10^{-2} \pm 3.6 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$1.64 \times 10^{-2} \pm 2.8 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$47.02\% \pm 10.95\%$
	16	$1.913 \times 10^{-2} \pm 9.2 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$1.17 \times 10^{-2} \pm 2.8 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$39.01\% \pm 14.92\%$
	32	$1.463 \times 10^{-2} \pm 5.1 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$9.1 \times 10^{-3} \pm 2.8 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$37.54\% \pm 19.56\%$
	64	$1.192 \times 10^{-2} \pm 3.1 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$7.8 \times 10^{-3} \pm 3.0 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$34.71\% \pm 25.31\%$
	128	$1.012 \times 10^{-2} \pm 2.7 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$6.9 \times 10^{-3} \pm 3.1 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$31.41\% \pm 30.80\%$
0.025	8	$3.91 \times 10^{-2} \pm 4.1 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$2.04 \times 10^{-2} \pm 3.2 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$47.82\% \pm 9.90\%$
	16	$2.42 \times 10^{-2} \pm 1.2 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$1.45 \times 10^{-2} \pm 3.5 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$39.96\% \pm 14.96\%$
	32	$1.837 \times 10^{-2} \pm 6.4 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$1.15 \times 10^{-2} \pm 3.6 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$37.39\% \pm 19.72\%$
	64	$1.492 \times 10^{-2} \pm 3.8 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$9.7 \times 10^{-3} \pm 3.7 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$34.82\% \pm 25.10\%$
	128	$1.266 \times 10^{-2} \pm 3.1 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$8.8 \times 10^{-3} \pm 4.0 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$30.87\% \pm 32.03\%$
0.03	8	$4.66 \times 10^{-2} \pm 4.6 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$2.48 \times 10^{-2} \pm 4.1 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$46.85\% \pm 10.15\%$
	16	$2.9 \times 10^{-2} \pm 1.4 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$1.74 \times 10^{-2} \pm 4.1 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$39.80\% \pm 14.31\%$
	32	$2.228 \times 10^{-2} \pm 7.9 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$1.38 \times 10^{-2} \pm 4.3 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$37.84\% \pm 19.45\%$
	64	$1.794 \times 10^{-2} \pm 5.6 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$1.17 \times 10^{-2} \pm 4.5 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$34.68\% \pm 25.33\%$
	128	$1.518 \times 10^{-2} \pm 3.4 \times 10^{-4}$	Yes	$1.05 \times 10^{-2} \pm 4.7 \times 10^{-3}$	Yes	$30.78\% \pm 30.93\%$

V. SIMULATIONS WITH SPAM ERRORS

TABLE IV: Performance Metrics with Coherent SPAM Error

M_k	RPE		BRPE		% Decrease in $\bar{\epsilon}$	% Increase in Δ_{th}
	$\bar{\epsilon}$	Δ_{th}	$\bar{\epsilon}$	Δ_{th}		
4	$7.9 \times 10^{-3} \pm 7.3 \times 10^{-3}$	0.167	$3.1 \times 10^{-3} \pm 4.6 \times 10^{-3}$	0.533	$60.10\% \pm 69.28\%$	218.29%
8	$2.4 \times 10^{-3} \pm 3.6 \times 10^{-3}$	0.375	$1.8 \times 10^{-3} \pm 3.4 \times 10^{-3}$	0.682	$24.95\% \pm 183.95\%$	81.59%
16	$2.9 \times 10^{-3} \pm 5.1 \times 10^{-3}$	0.576	$1.9 \times 10^{-3} \pm 4.2 \times 10^{-3}$	0.839	$32.31\% \pm 188.50\%$	45.53%
32	$1.0 \times 10^{-3} \pm 1.5 \times 10^{-3}$	0.925	$1.7 \times 10^{-3} \pm 3.3 \times 10^{-3}$	0.891	$-121.01\% \pm 622.06\%$	-3.64%

TABLE V: Performance Metrics with Coherent SPAM Error (Tailored Model)

M_k	RPE		BRPE		% Decrease in $\bar{\epsilon}$	% Increase in Δ_{th}
	$\bar{\epsilon}$	Δ_{th}	$\bar{\epsilon}$	Δ_{th}		
4	$7.9 \times 10^{-3} \pm 6.6 \times 10^{-3}$	0.167	$3.1 \times 10^{-3} \pm 3.2 \times 10^{-3}$	1.547	$60.52\% \pm 52.11\%$	824.30%
8	$4.7 \times 10^{-3} \pm 6.7 \times 10^{-3}$	0.404	$8.0 \times 10^{-4} \pm 8.4 \times 10^{-4}$	1.549	$83.22\% \pm 29.44\%$	282.99%
16	$2.3 \times 10^{-3} \pm 4.5 \times 10^{-3}$	0.595	$2.8 \times 10^{-4} \pm 3.0 \times 10^{-4}$	1.550	$87.99\% \pm 26.36\%$	160.54%
32	$2.3 \times 10^{-3} \pm 4.3 \times 10^{-3}$	0.912	$1.10 \times 10^{-4} \pm 5.9 \times 10^{-5}$	1.550	$95.24\% \pm 9.20\%$	70.05%

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work was supported by the Spectator Qubit Army Research Office MURI grant W911NF-18-1- 0218 and US Department of Energy grant DE-SC0019294.

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- [1] S. Kimmel, G. H. Low, T. J Yoder, "Robust calibration of a universal single-qubit gate set via robust phase estimation," Physical Review A, Vol. 92, 062315 (2015).